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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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PATHOGENETIC BASIS OF REPRODUCTIVE SYSTEM DISORDERS IN THE POST-INTENSIVE CARE PERIOD

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ANNOTATION

In the long-term periods of post-resuscitation disease (1 -, 2 -, 3-in months), pathogenetic disorders of the reproductive system are based on an increase in the indicators of the sympathetic nervous system, the prooxidant system, endogenous intoxication, a decrease in the coefficient of protein stability, a decrease in the number of glycoproteins in beta and delta basophil cells in the adenohypophysis, the amount of FSH, LH, hormones estradiol progesterone and primordial, primary, secondary, tertiary follicles, corpus luteum and an increase in atretic follicles in the ovary.

Keywords. Autonomic nervous system, MDA, catalase, MSM254, MSM280 FSH, LH, estradiol, progesterone, Ovaries.

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ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ НАРУШЕНИЙ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ В ПОСТРЕАНИМАЦИОННОМ ПЕРИОДЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В отдельных периодах постреанимационной болезни (в 1 -, 2 -, 3- месяцах) патогенетической основой нарушений репродуктивной системы является повышение показателей симпатической нервной системы, прооксидантной системы, эндогенная интоксикация, а также снижение коэффициента устойчивости белка, снижение количества гликопротеидов в бета- и дельта- базофильных клетках аденогипофиза, количества ФСГ, ЛГ, гормонов эстрадиола прогестерона и примордиальных, первичных, вторичных, третичных фолликулов, желтого тела и увеличение атретических фолликул в яичнике.

Ключевые слова. Автономная нервная система, МДА, каталаза, МСМ254, МСМ280, ФСГ, ЛГ, эстрадиол, прогестерон, яичник.

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POSTREANIMACION DAVRDA REPRODUKTIV TIZIMDA YUZAGA KELGAN BUZILISHLARINING PATOGENETIK ASOSLARI

ANNOTASIYA

Postreanimasion kasallikning uzoq davrlarida (1-,2-,3- oylarida) reproduktiv tizimning buzilishining patogenetik asosini postreanimasion davrning ortib borishiga mos ravishda simpatik nerv tizimining, prooksidant tizimining, endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichlarini ortib borishi, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichini pasayishi yotadi. Bunday o'zgarishlar orqali adenogipofizda beta va delta bazofil hujayralarida gilkoproteid miqdorini, qonda FSG, LG, estradiol gormonini, progesteron gormonlarini tuxumdonda primordial, birlamchi, ikkilamchi, uchlamchi follikulalarni, sariq dog'ni miqdorini kamayishi va atretik follikulalar miqdorini ortib borishi kuzatiladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Vegetativ asab tizimi, MDA, katalaza, MSM254, MSM280 FSh, LH, estradiol, progesteron, tuxumdon.

Kirish. Klinik o'lim yuqori darajali ekstremal faktorlar ta'siri oqibatida rivojlanib, inson organizimida to'qimalarning morfofunktsional reaktivligiga rezistentligi xos holda turli darajali o'zgarishlarni keltirib chiqaradi [16,3,13,14, 21,4,22,23,7,8,9]. Har qanday yuqori darajali ekstremal faktorlar inson organizimida birinchi o'rinda MNT sensor tizimi tekisligida o'z ta'sirini o'tkazadi va o'z navbatida ta'sirotda nisbatan javob reaksiyasi ta'minlanadi. Ta'sirotda nisbatan adaptiv jarayonlar birinchi o'rinda avtanom nerv tizimi neyroendokrin tizimi tekisligida amalga oshiriladi [1,4,10]. Agarda bu jaryonni Sel'e (1960) ma'lumotlariga asoslanib tahlil qilsak, bu jarayon uch bosqichda amalga oshadi: ya'ni qo'zg'alish, moslashish va toliqish. Gorizontov P.D.(1983) ma'lumotlariga etibor berilsa u besh bosqichda shakillanadi, ya'ni hujayra tekisligida energetik va tarkibiy qismlarni jalb etilishi; safarbar qilingan resurslarni faol bo'lmagan tizimlardan funktsional tizimga maqsadli o'tkazish; simpatoadrenal tizim, xamda stress gormonlari ta'sirida prooksidant tizimini faollashtirish; hujayrada energiya ta'minoti uchun katekolaminlar, glyukokortikoid gormonlar ta'sirida adenilat siklazing faollashishi; o'zoq muddatli moslashish uchun oqsil sintezining umumiy faollashuvini ta'minlash uchun anabolik jarayonning shakillanishi [20,21 2].

O'ta kuchli ekstremal ta'sirda yuzaga kelgan klinik o'limning keyingi postreanimasion davrida Gorizontov ma'lumotlariga ko'ra bosqichli moslashish jarayonlari shakillanadi. Lekin postreanimasion kasallikning uzoq davrlarida yuzaga keladigan yetishmovchilik mexanizmlari to'liqligicha o'rganilmagan va bu dolzarb muammo bo'lib hisoblanadi. Shundan kelib chiqib moslashish reaksiyaning beshinchi bosqichida o'zoq muddatli moslashish jarayoning reproduktiv tizimda boradigan buzilishlarining patogenetik asoslarini o'rganish maqsadga muvoviqdir.

Ishning maqsadi. Urg'ochi kalamushlarning diestrus davrida 10 daqiqali klinik o'limdan keyingi yuzaga kelgan postreanimasion kasallikning uzoq davrlarida reproduktiv tizimda yuzaga kelgan buzilishlarining patogenetik asoslarini aniqlash.

Tadqiqot ob'ekti. Izlanish voyaga yetgan urg'ochi 20 ta vazni160-180 gr tashkil etgan, zotsiz, oq kalamushlarda olib borildi va ularda postreanimasion davrning 1-,2-,3-oylarida avtanom nerv tizimi, prooksidant, antioksidant endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichlarida, hamda reproduktiv tizimda yuzaga keladigan o'zgarishlar o'rganildi.

Tadqiqot usullari. Klinik o'lim va postreanimasion kasallik Korpachev V.G.(1982) usuli yordamida modellashtirildi va shu bilan bir qatorda avtanom nerv tizimining reaktivligi [19], beta va

delta bazofil hujayralaridagi morfofunktsional aktivligi [15], qondagi MDA miqdori [18], katalaza miqdori [11], MSM254 va MSM280 oqsilni chidamlilik koeffisienti [5] dinamikasi o'rganildi. Statistik tahlil Microsoft Office – Excel 2000 standart paketi yordamida amalga oshirildi.

Olingan natijalar va uning muxokamasi. Postreanimayion davrning 1- oyiga kelib, kalamushlarda postreanimasion davrning yigirma birinchi kuniga nisbatan Hildebrant koeffisientini 1,1 martaga oshgan bo'lib, simpatik nerv tizimining reaktivligining ustunligi aniqlandi. Prooksidant, antioksidant tizimida esa MDA/katalaza koeffisienti esa 2,7 marta oshganligi, endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichida esa MSM254 1,8 marta ortgan, MSM280 esa 1,8 martaga kamaygan bo'lib, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichi esa 1,01 martaga oshganligi kuzatildi. Bu vaqtda qonda FSG avvalgi ko'rsatkichga ko'ra 1,13 martaga, LG -1,19 martaga, estradiol - 1,06 martaga, progesteron gormonining miqdori esa 1,1 martaga kamayganligi aniqlandi. Olingan natijalarni intakt hayonlar ko'rsatkichi bilan solishtirganda, Hildebrant koeffisienti 1,07 marta yuqori bo'lib, qonda FSG miqdori 1,05 marta, estradiol gormonining miqdori esa 1,16 marta gacha kamayganligi kuzatildi. Pro va antioksidant tizimida MDA/katalaza koeffisienti 1,42 marta, hamda endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichida MSM254 miqdori 1,25 marta yuqori bo'lib, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichini 1,33 martaga past ekanligi isbotlandi. Tuxumdonda po'stloq qismida primordial follikulalar miqdori intakt hayvonlar guruhiga qaraganda 1,2 marta, birlamchi follikulalar 1,23 marta, ikkilamchi follikulalar 1,26 martaga, uchlamchi follikulalar esa 1,59 martaga, sariq dog' esa 1.5 martaga kamaygan bo'lib, atretik follikulalar soni esa 1,7 martaga ortganligi aniqlandi ($P < 0,05$).

Postreanimayion davrning 2-oyiga kelib, kalamushlarda Hildebrant koeffisientini postreanimasion davrning birinchi kuniga nisbatan 1,01 marta kam bo'lib, simpatik nerv tizimining reaktivligini saqlanganligi kuzatildi. Bu vaqtda qonda FSG miqdori esa 1,6 martaga, LG 1,8 martagacha, estradiol 1,47 martagacha, progesteron gormonini miqdori esa 3,1 martagacha kamayganligi kuzatildi. Prooksidant tizimida MDA miqdori 2,25 martaga kam, antioksidant tizimida katalaza miqdori esa 1,5 marta yuqori bo'lib, MDA/katalaza koeffisienti esa 2,67 barobarga oshganligi aniqlandi. Endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichida esa MSM 254 1,83 martaga, MSM 280 esa 1,75 martaga, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichi esa 1,05 marta past holatda saqlanganligi kuzatildi. Bu vaqtga kelib, olingan natijalarni intakt hayonlar ko'rsatkichi bilan solishtirganda, Hildebrant koeffisienti 1,09 marta yuqori bo'lib, qonda FSG miqdori 1,12 marta, estradiol gormonining miqdori esa 1,22 marta past ekanligi qayd etildi. Pro va antioksidant tizimida MDA/katalaza koeffisienti 1,31 marta yuqori bo'lib, endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichida MSM254 miqdori kerak 1,34 marta yuqori bo'lib MSM 280 kerak, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichini 1,43 martaga past ekanligi kuzatildi. Tuxumdonda po'stloq qismida primordial follikulalar miqdori intakt hayvonlar guruhiga qaraganda 1,33 marta, birlamchi follikulalar 1,35 marta, ikkilamchi follikulalar 1,46 martaga, uchlamchi follikulalar esa 1,84 martaga, sariq dog' esa 1,6 martaga kamaygan bo'lib, atretik follikulalar soni esa 1,9 martaga ortganligi aniqlandi ($P < 0,01$).

Postreanimayion davrning 3-oyiga kelib, hayvonlarda Hildebrant koeffisientini intakt guruhidagi hayvonlarning ko'rsatkichidan 1,1 martaga yuqori bo'lib, simpatik nerv tizimining reaktivligini saqlanganligi aniqlandi. Bu vaqtda qonda prooksidant, antioksidant tizimida esa MDA/katalaza koeffisienti esa 1,3 marta yuqori ko'rsatkichga ega bo'ldi. Endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichida esa MSM254 1,33 past darajada, MSM280 kerak yuqori, oqsilning chidamlilik ko'rsatkichi esa 1,43 barobarga, FSG miqdori esa 1,12 martaga, LG 1,4 martaga, estradiol 1,2 martaga, progesteron gormonlarining 1,3 martagacha pasayganligi kuzatildi. Tuxumdonda primordial follikulalar miqdori intakt hayvonlar guruhiga qaraganda 1,44 marta, birlamchi follikulalar 1,53 marta, ikkilamchi follikulalar 1,64 martaga, uchlamchi follikulalar esa 2,19 martaga, sariq dog' esa 1,7 martaga kamaygan bo'lsa, atretik follikulalar soni esa 2,1 martaga ortganligi aniqlandi ($P < 0,01$).

Olingan ma'lumotlarni Gorizontov (1993) ma'lumotlari bilan solishtirilganda, adaptasiya jarayonining oxirgi bosqichining ishdan chiqishi kelib chiqib, reproduktiv tizimda simpatik nerv tizimining, prooksidant tizimining, endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichlarini ortib bordi. Oqsilning chidamlilik ko'rsatkichini, adenogipofizda beta va delta bazofil hujayralarida glikoproteid miqdorini, qonda FSG, LG, va o'z navbatda follikularining estradiol gormonini, progesteron gormonlarini miqdorini kamayib borishi asosiy o'rinlardan birini egallaganligi yotadi.

Xulosa

Postreanimasion kasallikning uzoq davrlarida (1-,2-,3- oylarida) reproduktiv tizimning buzilishining patogenetik asosini, postreanimasion davrning ortib borishiga mos ravishda simpatik nerv tizimining, prooksidant tizimining, endogen intoksikasiya ko'rsatkichlarini ortib borishi, oqsilni chidamlilik ko'rsatkichini pasayishi yotadi. Bunday o'garishlar orqali adenogipofizda beta va delta bazofil hujayralarida gilkoproteid miqdorining o'zgarishi, qonda esa FSG, LG, estradiol gormonini, hamda progesteron gormonlarining son ko'rsatkichlarining pasayishi tashkil etdi. Mazkur jarayonda tuxumdonda primordial, birlamchi, ikkilamchi, uchlamchi follikulalarni va sariq dog'ni miqdorini kamayishi, atretik follikulalar miqdorini ortib borishi qayd etildi.

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